

Community Empowerment of Coffee Farmers in Improving the Welfare of Arabica Coffee Farmers in Dogiyai Regency, Papua Province

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ABSTRACT: *This research is based on the empowerment of coffee farming communities in improving their welfare which is essentially one solution. But in reality in Dogiyai Regency the empowerment of coffee farmers has not been able to improve the welfare of Arabica coffee farmers. The purpose of this study was to identify and analyze the community empowerment of coffee farmers in improving the welfare of Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency, Papua Province. This research is based on the concept of community empowerment theory according to Suharto, (2015: 67) which is called the concept of community empowerment theory which includes possibility, strength, protection, support and maintenance.*

The research method used in this study is a qualitative research method with construction characteristics built based on natural conditions, more descriptive in nature, while data obtained through data collection techniques of observation, interviews and documentation. The results showed that the empowerment of coffee farming communities in improving the welfare of Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency, Papua Province was still not going well in accordance with the policy of the Dogiyai Regency Regional Government to focus on providing facilities and infrastructure compared to the ability of the coffee farming community, this was shown by the weakness of the community. possible, in support of the atmosphere of community potential and the culture of the Arabica coffee farming community in Dogiyai Regency. The lack of knowledge strengthening in solving problems that exist in the coffee farming community and has not been supported by the ability to develop the confidence of the coffee farming community in Dogiyai Regency. The local government of Dogiyai Regency is still weak in protecting the weak community of coffee farmers and there is still discrimination against coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency. Lack of support for guidance and support so that they are able to carry out their roles and duties as coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency. Lack of maintenance of conducive conditions in obtaining business opportunities as coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency as well as balance in obtaining business opportunities as Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency. Then the coffee farmer empowerment model found in this study in Dogiyai Regency, Papua Province is through the process of providing researchers and counseling, providing guidance prioritizing aspects of possibility, providing changes in knowledge, attitudes and skills, increasing productivity and income and realizing empowerment and welfare.

Keywords: *Empowerment, Community and Welfare*

I. Introduction

The development of the plantation sector in Indonesia has greatly benefited from the results that have been achieved so far. This is undeniable considering that Indonesia has a very large natural resource wealth capital, thus providing opportunities for the development of plantation businesses, one of which is coffee, which is one of the plantation commodities that is widely cultivated by farmers and private companies. This is because this commodity has a high economic value and is strategic, both for increasing farmers' income and even increasing foreign exchange for the country. Coffee is a type of tropical plant, which can grow anywhere, except in places that are too high with very cold temperatures or barren areas that are not suitable for coffee plant life.

The government itself in developing the coffee plantation sector has issued Presidential Decree of the Republic of Indonesia Number 21 of 2018 concerning the National Strategy for the Acceleration of Development of Disadvantaged Regions 2015-2019 which aims to build synergy and synchronization of policies and programs to accelerate development of underdeveloped regions nationally (Purnomo, D Daraba, M Achmad, I Tahir. 2021). Dogiyai Regency's income in 2013 was IDR 580.88 billion, increased to IDR 755.19 billion or experienced a growth of 30.01 percent in 2014 which was the highest growth compared to the following years. However, in the following years, it also increased to Rp. 882.58 billion in 2016.

The main source of regional income in Dogiyai Regency comes from transfer income/balancing funds with an average proportion of 80.07 percent per year. The proportion of regional transfer revenue components that provide the largest contribution in the formation of transfer income/balancing funds in Dogiyai Regency comes from general allocation funds with an average of 76.85 percent per year. The proportion of regional income components shows changes every year. The proportion of the original regional income component has shown an increase since 2013 which is 0.92 percent, increasing to 1.04 percent in 2014 and rising to 1.03 percent in 2015 then in 2016 to 1.18 percent. Meanwhile, the proportion of regional income for the transfer/balancing fund income component decreased from 84.36 percent in 2013 to 77.46 percent in 2014 and then increased again in 2015 to 79.84 percent and decreased to 78.63 percent in 2015. 2016. For the proportion of regional income in other components of legitimate regional income, the proportion also changes such as the component of regional original income and transfer income/balancing funds, for example in 2013 other legitimate regional income has a proportion of 1.16 percent then in 2013 in 2014 increased sharply to 5.50 percent, but decreased again to 0.30 percent in 2015 and increased again in 2016 to 3.75 percent.

This shows that each year's regional income has a different proportion or tends to fluctuate during 2013-2016 for each component in regional income which is a source of financing to finance local government programs/activities in Dogiyai district. Dogiyai Regency's regional income has shown a positive increase since 2014 by 101.82 percent, but decreased in 2014. Realization of regional income only reached 99.69 percent of the target set. Realization of regional income in the following years 2014, 2015 and 2016 continued to decline from the set target.

Dogiyai Regency's human development is not yet fully visible. Education is the main agenda for human development in Dogiyai Regency. This is what makes one of the focuses of education in Dogiyai Regency which continues to be addressed by inviting all stakeholders, especially the organizers of the education unit, both the principal and the education office to continue to work better than before. The Dogiyai Regency Government continues to improve a number of educational facilities and infrastructure, including the availability of representative schools and study rooms in a number of educational units. The availability of teaching staff is evenly distributed throughout the Dogiyai area, in order to minimize the gap between schools in cities and rural areas. As is known, education is an important thing that can change the quality of human resources for the better. However, in Dogiyai district, the issue of education is still a tough job for the local government.

In addition to access to educational facilities, other problems, such as the shortage of teachers and inadequate educational facilities, are still a scourge that tarnishes the development of education in Dogiyai.

Specifically for the number of teachers in Dogiyai, there were 742 teachers spread across 78 schools, both public and private. However, this number is not balanced with equal distribution of teachers, so that there are still many areas in Dogiyai that lack teachers. The Department of Education, as the party most responsible for this, is working hard to improve education services, one of which is the preparation of educators. This is illustrated by the holding of training or workshops or the like. This is an effort by the district government to facilitate teachers and schools, so that teachers can improve their discipline according to their duties and responsibilities. In addition, the Education Office will also make efforts so that students can get affirmation scholarships and can cooperate with universities, so that when they graduate from high school / vocational school, they can immediately continue their education to college. Based on the problems mentioned above, the researcher is interested in conducting research and putting it into a dissertation entitled: Community Empowerment of Coffee Farmers in Improving the Welfare of Arabica Coffee Farmers in Dogiyai Regency, Papua Province.

II. Methods

Research is a long process, starting from the interest that exists in a person to understand certain phenomena which then develop into ideas, theories and concepts. Research design according to Silalahi (2006:167) is an investigation plan and structure that is structured in such a way that the author will be able to obtain answers to his research questions.

The statement above explains that the research design provides a guide for the author to conduct research. In addition, with the research design, the author can predict the data that must be completed and the level of difficulty that will be faced. For this reason, it is very necessary to design research with appropriate, suitable or appropriate methods so that research becomes more focused. The research method in this case serves to answer the problems raised in the research. This method is used to carry out research systematically so that research activities to writing a dissertation are an inseparable unit. According to Nazir (1999:94), said that "research is a systematic process over a long period of time using scientific methods and applicable rules". According to Sugiyono (2013:1) suggests that "research method is a method or method used to obtain data with a specific purpose".

The research method used to analyze the community empowerment of coffee farmers in improving the welfare of Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency, Papua Province, is a qualitative research method. Furthermore, with the same intention, Sugiyono (2013:6) suggests that the qualitative method is a research method used to examine the condition of natural objects (as opposed to experiments) where the author is the key instrument. The data collection technique is done by triangulation (combined), the resulting data is descriptive, and the data analysis is done inductively. The results of qualitative research emphasize meaning rather than generalization. In this study, the author uses a qualitative method with an inductive descriptive approach. According to Nazir (2005:63), descriptive method is a method in examining the status of a group of people, an object, a condition, a system of thought or a class of present events. The purpose of this descriptive research is to make a systematic, factual and accurate descriptive, picture or painting about the factors as well as the properties and relationships between the phenomena being investigated.

Understanding the inductive approach according to Nazir (2005:202), is "a way of thinking to give reasons starting with specific statements to compose a general argument". The reason the author uses a qualitative method with an inductive descriptive approach in this study is because the author wants to know clearly about the empowerment of coffee farming communities in improving the welfare of Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency, Papua Province, where the author tries to describe, describe and report an object which is then discussed to obtain information. general conclusion.

III. General Results & Conclusion

Dogiyai Regency is one of the regencies located in the central mountainous region between Nabire Regency and Paniai Regency which is geographically located at a position of 30057'-4015 South Latitude and 135020-136037' East Longitude.

The administrative position also regulates the boundaries of the Dogiyai Regency area with a number of adjoining regencies, namely:

- To the north it is bordered by Siriwo District in Nabire Regency.
- To the south, it is bordered by the West Mimika District, Mimika Regency.
- In the west it is bordered by Kaimana Regency and Uwapa District, Nabire Regency.
- In the east it is bordered by the West Paniai District, Paniai Regency.

Based on the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 8 of 2008 the Dogiyai Regency is said to have an area of approximately 4,237.4 Km². Because it is located in a mountainous area, almost 85% of the area is mountainous. However, Dogiyai Regency still has fertile natural forests with a wealth of potential forest resources that are quite abundant and very promising for the welfare of the community in the long term.

Based on the Dogiyai Regency BPS census, the population of Dogiyai Regency in 2016 was 89,327 by sex, with 44,913 men and 44,414 women. Meanwhile, in 2013 the population of Dogiyai Regency was 84,903 people with a male population of 42,802 and a female population of 42,101. Then in 2015 the population of Dogiyai Regency amounted to 87,728 people with a male population of 43,416 and a female population of 43,416.

In this period, population growth is quite slow. This is certainly due to many factors, so that through this struggle, if elected, the population situation will be regulated to improve the quality of human life so that it can increase the population while still paying attention to the condition and health of the population, especially the female population.

Dogiyai Regency is in a strategic position because it is flanked by Nabire Regency and Deiyai and Paniai Regency, so it is a buffer area and has regional potential to be developed in the context of improving the economy and welfare of the people of Dogiyai Regency, the superior potential of the area that needs to be developed and has promising economic prospects, namely :

1. Agriculture

Types of crops that are suitable for cultivation in Dogiyai Regency are as follows: Sweet Potatoes, Keladi, Bete, highland vegetables, corn, peanuts, soybeans and passion fruit.

2. Ranch

Dogiyai District is an area suitable for developing pig, cattle, goat and rabbit farming. All types of livestock are growing quite rapidly and are a promising economic prospect and can be developed to meet the increasing demand for fresh meat every year, both locally and to meet the demand for meat from Paniai and Deiyai Regencies.

3. Fishing

Freshwater fisheries can be developed in Kamuu District, Dogiyai District, North Kamuu District, East Kamuu District and South Kamuu District, so it is expected to support the increasing local consumption needs of freshwater fish in Dogiyai District.

4. Plantation and Forestry

Potential areas in the plantation sector, mostly in the lowlands and hills, while the highlands have promising prospects for the development of production plants, especially Arabica coffee, cocoa and oil palm as well as production forests spread over 10 (ten) Districts.

Based on the explanations in the previous chapters, especially to answer the questions asked in chapter I of this research, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Empowerment of coffee farming communities in improving the welfare of Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency, Papua Province is still not going well according to theory or less successful because it focuses on providing facilities and infrastructure compared to the ability of coffee farming communities. -the following:

- a. Dimensions of Possibility, there is still weak support for the atmosphere of community potential and the culture of the Arabica coffee farming community in Dogiyai Regency.
- b. Dimensions of Reinforcement, lack of knowledge to solve problems that exist in the coffee farming community and have not been supported by the ability to develop the self-confidence of the coffee farming community in Dogiyai Regency.
- c. Dimensions of Protection, the local government of Dogiyai Regency is still weak in protecting the weak community of coffee farmers and there is still discrimination against coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency.
- d. Dimensions of Support, lack of guidance and support in order to be able to carry out their roles and duties as coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency.
- e. Maintenance dimension, there is still a lack of maintaining conducive conditions in obtaining business opportunities as coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency and the balance of obtaining business opportunities as Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency.

2. Inhibiting and supporting factors for community empowerment of coffee farmers in improving the welfare of Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency, Papua Province, among others: Inhibiting factors include weak extension programs, limited competitive markets, limited services and weak agricultural product markets, while supporting factors are the motivation of farming communities and local government policies of Dogiyai District

3. The model of community empowerment of coffee farmers in improving the welfare of Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency, Papua Province based on the results of the discussion of community empowerment analysis and the inhibiting and supporting factors, it was found a model that is considered relevant and good to be used in empowering coffee farmers through the following process:

The Dogiyai Regency Government through researchers and extension workers provides guidance to coffee farming communities by prioritizing the empowerment aspect by maintaining an atmosphere of potential and changing the inhibiting culture. aspects of strengthening through access to information and financial support, aspects of protection through protecting the weak and eliminating discrimination, aspects of support through guidance and support, aspects of elections through maintaining conducive conditions and balance in obtaining business opportunities. After that, it provides changes in knowledge, attitudes and skills of coffee farmers and then increases the productivity and income of coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency so that the empowerment and welfare of Arabica Coffee Farmers in Dogiyai Regency is realized.

Referring to the facts in the field and the results of the discussion of this research, there are several suggestions that are considered important to convey, namely:

1. Theoretical

Based on the results of the discussion of this study, for researchers who concentrate on theories of community empowerment according to Suharto, (2015:67) through qualitative research, we suggest to be able to develop

a theory of community empowerment in improving welfare, especially with regard to the following dimensions:

- a. Possibility, which is a measure of the potential and cultural atmosphere that hinders coffee farming communities in improving the welfare of Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency.
- b. Strengthening, which is a measure for problem-solving knowledge and the ability to develop the confidence of the coffee farming community in improving the welfare of Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency.
- c. Protection, which is a measure to protect the weak and eliminate discrimination against Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency.
- d. Support, which is a measure for guidance so that they are able to carry out their roles and duties as well as support to be able to carry out their roles and duties as coffee farmers in improving the welfare of Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency.
- e. Maintenance which is a measure to maintain conducive conditions in obtaining business opportunities and the balance of obtaining business opportunities as coffee farmers in improving the welfare of Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency

In addition to the dimensions of the community empowerment process above, it is also necessary to develop community empowerment in improving welfare.

2. Practical

- a. It is necessary to understand the potential and cultural atmosphere that hinders coffee farming communities in improving the welfare of Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency.
- b. It is necessary to have knowledge of problem solving and the ability to develop the confidence of the coffee farming community in improving the welfare of Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency.
- c. There needs to be an understanding of protecting the weak and eliminating discrimination against Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency.
- d. Guidance is needed to be able to carry out their roles and duties as well as support to be able to carry out their roles and duties as coffee farmers in improving the welfare of Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency.
- e. It is necessary to maintain conducive conditions in obtaining business opportunities and the balance of obtaining business opportunities as coffee farmers in improving the welfare of Arabica coffee farmers in Dogiyai Regency.

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